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Diversity of molluscs in the Bagoue region (Côte d'Ivoire): Influence of seasons

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Abstract

Côte d'Ivoire finds itself lacking in animal proteins despite the multiple efforts made to achieve food self-sufficiency for its population. Indeed, natural resources capable of guaranteeing food security are under pressure from humans (destruction of forests and wildlife and action of bush fires). Thus, our work was carried out in the Bagoué region in the north of Côte d'Ivoire. From January 2018 to December 2019 (2 years), we inventoried 7 species of mollusks divided into 5 families according to the two well-defined dry and rainy seasons. To carry out our work, the Bagoué region was divided into six zones. We demarcated quadrats of 200 m² in three villages chosen in each zone. To do this, we searched in the ground, the litter, on the leaves and tree trunks and then on the trees. The identification of molluscs was carried out using morphological criteria. Our study recorded 5089 ± 47.97 *Achatina fulica* (324 ± 9.13 in dry season and 4765 ± 38.84 in rainy season), 1794 ± 17.18 *Laristes varicus* (144 ± 1.02 in dry season and 1650 ± 15.97 in rainy season), 991 ± 22.45 *Archachatina ventricosa* (40 ± 2.2 in dry season and 951 ± 20.25 in rainy season), 968 ± 9.87 *Limicolaria flammea* (9 ± 0.99 in dry season and 959 ± 19.86 in rainy season), 444 ± 2.39 *Gabbiella africana* (432 ± 41.12 in dry season and 309 ± 38.21 in rainy season), 271 ± 1.44 *Limacus flavus* (12 ± 10.11 in dry season and 254 ± 23.28 in rainy season) and 187 ± 1.21 *Mytilis edulis* (36 ± 11.20 in dry season and 151 ± 21.02 in rainy season). At the end of our study, it appears that in the natural environment, the 7 species of molluscs collected vary according to the seasons. The populations of Bagoué, through their activities (bush fires, deforestation, slash-and-burn cultivation) have a considerable impact on the biotope. These activities could be a danger to the survival of molluscs. Thus, we suggest raising awareness among populations on environmental protection, strengthening measures for the protection and conservation of animal and plant species.

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Introduction

The degradation of natural ecosystems is accentuated by the aridity of the climate which has become a worrying phenomenon in humid tropical zones (Thiombiano, 2005). Despite this aridity, animal and plant species survive there. Ivory Coast, particularly in the Bagoué region in the north, in the savannah district, is at the heart of this daily degradation. For Achard *et al.* (2002) and Anonymous (2014), the Ivorian forest has experienced rapid degradation. It increased from 16.5 million hectares in 1960 to 4 million in 2000 and then to 2.97 million hectares in 2014. According to Brooks *et al.* (2002) this deforestation results in the degradation and loss of natural habitats. This is the main cause of the massive disappearance of species such as molluscs in these environments. The diversity and distribution of these molluscs are determined by environmental factors, namely air humidity, temperature, litter thickness, altitude, soil type (Bruggen, 1969; 1995; Peake, 1978; Tattersfield, 1990; Welter-Schultes, 2000), the type of habitat (Cameron *et al.*, 2007; Memel *et al.*, 2009; Oke and Chokor, 2009; Tattersfield *et al.*, 2001) and the availability of food resources (Memel, 2009). Little work has been devoted to the ecology and diversity of molluscs in Côte d'Ivoire. The oldest work carried out took place at Mount Nimba in the west of Côte d'Ivoire. Forcart (1953) studied the Veronicidae. Gaillard (1954) worked on the genus *Curvella*. Binder (1963; 1976) and Van Mol (1970) worked on Urocyclidae. Lamotte and Roy (2003) also studied these mollusks. The most recent work was carried out by (Memel, 2009) on the Achatinidae family within the Banco National Park. In the Yapo classified forest, (Amani, 2018) worked on the biodiversity and ecology of Gastropod molluscs. At the National Floristic Center of Abidjan Cocody (N'dri, 2021) carried out work on the biodiversity and ecology of terrestrial gastropod molluscs. The choice of the Bagoué region is justified by the fact that it is subject to anthropogenic pressures such as the collection of snails by populations, bush fires, field work,

trampling by livestock and the long dry season. In addition, this study can contribute, for vulnerable species such as Molluscs (Lydeard *et al.*, 2004; Régnier *et al.*, 2015), or Invertebrates in general (Cardoso *et al.*, 2011), to their better taken into account in conservation strategies, particularly in the context of current issues linked to the massive erosion of biodiversity (Barnosky *et al.*, 2011; Pimm *et al.*, 2014). Knowledge of the mollusks of this region could strengthen its conservation.

The general objective of this work is to determine the diversity of molluscs in the said region.

It will be specifically:

1. To study the physicochemical conditions of the Bagoué region;
2. Make a qualitative (specific diversity) and quantitative (abundance) inventory of molluscs.

Materials and methods

Study area

The Bagoué region includes three departments, namely Boundiali (4302 km²), Kouto (4164 km²) and Tengrela (2202 km²). An integral part of the savannahs district, it is located between 08°11'27" and 10°64'28" north latitudes and 06°25'89" and 06°84'62" west longitudes. It is located at an altitude varying between 333 to 436 meters (Garmin GPSMap 64S). Boundiali, regional capital, is located approximately 100 kilometers from the town of Korhogo and 659 kilometers north of Abidjan. It is limited to the south by the Worodougou and Béré regions, to the east by the Poro region, to the west by the Kabadougou and Folon regions and in its northern part by the Republic of Mali (Fig. 1). It covers a total area of 10,668 km² for a population of 375,687 inhabitants, all districts combined.

Biological materials

In this study, the biological material used is composed of gastropod molluscs (snails and slugs) and bivalves from the Bagoué region.

Fig. 1. Location of the studysite in the north of the Ivory Coast in the Bagoué region

Technical materials

For the study of specific richness and abundance, the material used consisted of:

1. a 20 m long tape measure was used to measure the dimensions of the quadrats;
2. a ribbon for demarcating quadrats. The ribbon being fixed on stakes at the four corners of the quadrat;
3. a digital caliper for measuring the shell;
4. an electronic scale for measuring the live weight of specimens of *Archachatina ventricosa*;
5. a box of white oil paint and cotton swabs for marking *Archachatina ventricosa*;
6. a GARMIN brand GPS (Geographic Position System) (model GPSMAP64s) was used to record the geographic coordinates of the sampling sites and molluscs;
7. a camera for taking pictures.

Qualitative and quantitative inventory of molluscs

In practice, we have divided the Bagoué region into six large zones (Zone I, Zone II, Zone III, Zone IV, Zone V and Zone VI). Each zone has seven villages. In each zone, three squares were demarcated. The sampling plan was stratified sampling. This type of sampling consists of observing in the selected plots stratum by stratum (in the soil, litter, on grasses, trunks then branches and leaves). It provides information on the entire study area and requires less time (Oke and Alohan, 2006; Oke and Chokor, 2009; Wronski and Hausdorf, 2009; Oke, 2013).

The study lasted six months from May to November 2018. The choice of this period is justified by the rainy period. This is the period during which the abundance and specific richness of mollusks are highest. As for the study of dynamics, it lasted 24 months. It started in January 2018 and ended in December 2019; Sampling was done once a month.

In these plots, the sampling method used for the inventory of snails, slugs and bivalves is sampling on a defined surface or squares method combined with "sight" sampling, sampling by volume of defined litter or the method volume and sampling by trapping

using buried pots Thus, squares of 400 m² (20 m long by 20 m wide) were demarcated at different locations in the plot (Dyduch-Falniowska and Tobis, 1989; Oke, 2013; Amani, 2018). The principle of the method is based on the collection of all individuals of all large species present within the defined surface area. The establishment of the zones took into account a certain number of criteria, in particular, the difficulties in accessing the site (presence of rivers, lowlands or hills, mango, cashew and cotton plantations), the appearance of the plant cover (regrowth of grass and shrubs). These criteria made it possible to define, a priori, forty-two (42) villages in the Bagoué region. During the survey, a certain number of plots presented similar climatic (temperature, relative humidity) and biotic (species of molluscs present) characteristics. This allowed us to maintain three squares in each of the six zones (18 squares).

Species identification

The identification was made using different determination keys (Bequaert, 1950; Abbott, 1989; Daget, 2003; Rowson, 2014; Vrignaud, 2010; Oke, 2013) Welter-Schultes, 2012; Kerney and Cameron, 2015; Wiktor, 1983, 1987, 2000) and current available literature. It was confirmed at the laboratory level of the Animal Production research center, by Professor

Otchoumou

Atcho of Nangui Abrogoua University, Dr. Aman Jean Baptiste research fellow at Nangui Abrogoua University.

*Statistical analysis**Kohonen self-organizing card*

In our study, Kohonen's self-organizing map algorithm was used (Kohonen, 1982, 1995, 2001). The plots were ordered according to species assemblages (abundance). This method has the advantage of visually representing simplified profiles from complex databases by identifying similar groups (Lek *et al.*, 2000; Kohonen, 2001). Kohonen's self-organizing map was produced using the XLSTAT program version 2021.3.1.

Principal component analysis (PCA)

Principal components analysis (PCA) is a descriptive factorial statistical method whose objective is to process in a more synthetic way files comprising different samples (individuals) affected by several parameters (quantitative variables) (Philippeau, 1992). The data matrix is made up of samples “n” in rows on which quantitative variables “p” are measured arranged in columns. The matrix used in this study is a base having undergone a logarithmic transformation “log (X + 1)” to have an approximate normality then standardized and obtain a comparable scale of the variables (the species in our case) (Michael *et al.*, 2004). These calculations were made using the XLSTAT program version 2021.3.1.

Chi-square test

This test is used to assess the existence or not of a relationship between two characters within a population. Either when these characters are qualitative or one character is quantitative and the other qualitative, or when the two characters are quantitative but the values have been grouped together. These calculations were made using the XLSTAT program version 2021.3.1.

Results

Typology of plots

An ascending hierarchical classification of the areas having been the subject of quantitative sampling of molluscs was carried out on the basis of certain abiotic parameters (river, lowlands, hills, joints of the rocks in the environment, plantations). It made it possible to distinguish two types of habitats (Fig. 2).

The semi-open habitats (HSO: I) contain 11 villages with moderate human activity: Kouto, Tindara, Kolia, Papara, Kanakono, Gbénu, Zanasso, Diogo, Kantara, Blédiéméné, Monogo. This type of habitat is characterized by a forest reforested by *Tectona grandis* trees, a moderately dense forest (sacred and/or classified forest), by fruit trees, a moderately dense undergrowth and a litter thickness of approximately 6 cm.

Fig. 2. Hierarchical classification of sampled areas based on certain abiotic parameters

I: Semi-open habitats (HSO); Open habitats (HO): IIa, IIb and IIc

The second (II) consists of open habitats (HO: II). It is characterized by grassy savannah, plantations (fruit trees) of mango and cashew trees and regrowth of shrubs. In this open habitat, there are also lowlands and rivers, the 31 villages are subdivided into three subgroups:

1. The subgroup (IIa) with 11 villages namely Kasséré, Kounoumon, Nongana, Niempurgué, Fafala, San, Tengrela, Néguépié, Tiasso, Mahandianaba, Diamankani. The thickness of the litter is approximately 4.3 cm.
2. The second subgroup (IIb) includes 12 villages including Koffré, N'déou, Tounvré, Niguédougou, Gbando, Boundiali, N'dara, Siénré, Débété, Blésségoué, Mahalé, Sanhala. The thickness of the litter is approximately 4.7 cm.
3. The third subgroup (IIc) with 8 villages which are Sissédougou, Siempurgo, Ganaoni, Karakpo, Kébi, M'bia, Monogo, Guinguéréni. The thickness of the litter is approximately 4.9 cm.

Diversity of mollusks harvested in the Bagoué region

Qualitative inventory

During the two years (January 2018 to December 2019) of sampling, we collected seven species of molluscs divided into six genera and five families.

Family Achatinidae

This family, in the Bagoué region, is made up of three genera and three species: the genus *Achatina* with the species *Achatina fulica*, the genus *Archachatina* with the species *Archachatina ventricosa* and the genus *Limicolaria* with the species *Limicolaria flammea* (Fig. 3A, B and C).

Fig. 3. Famille des Achatinidae

Family Bithyniidae

This family includes a single genus and one species: the genus *Gabbiella* with the species *Gabbiella africana* (Fig. 4).

Gabbiella africana: A: face dorsale et B: face ventrale

Fig. 4. Famille des Bithyniidae

Family Ampullariidae

It has a single genus and one species: the genus *Laristes* with the species *Laristes varicus* (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Famille des Ampullariidae

Family Mytilidae

This family includes a single genus and one species: the genus *Mytilis* with the species *Mytilis edulis* (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Famille des Mytilidae

Family Limacidae

This family includes a single genus and one species: the genus *Limacus* with the species *Limacus flavus* (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. Famille des Limacidae

Quantitative inventory

The relative abundance of the identified mollusk families is shown in Fig. 8. This abundance varies from one quadrat to another (Table 1). Each quadrat provided between 198 to 306 individuals with an average of 232 ± 26.04 individuals. According to Fig. 8, the most abundant family Achatinidae (7048 individuals) is represented with a percentage of 72.33%, followed by Ampullariidae (1794 individuals) and Bithyniidae (444 individuals) with 18.41% and 4, 56% respectively. The Limacidae family (with 271 individuals or 2.78%) and Bivalves (with 187 individuals or 1.92%) are the least represented. We inventoried 9744 molluscs in the different study areas.

Table 1. Numerical abundance and specific richness of mollusks harvested in the Bagoué region

Taxons	Squares																		Total number of individuals per square
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	
Achatinidae																			
<i>Achatina fulica</i>	432	324	112	321	114	432	343	123	209	213	236	344	542	321	111	131	328	453	5089
<i>Archachatina ventricosa</i>	53	43	34	65	67	87	90	32	23	0	44	67	56	50	77	60	56	87	991
<i>Limicolaria flammea</i>	76	98	79	57	46	45	87	30	25	16	45	56	67	45	43	67	54	32	968
Bithyniidae																			
<i>Gabbiella africana</i>	34	12	34	54	0	30	23	54	12	10	12	11	15	17	56	34	21	15	444
Ampullariidae																			
<i>Lanistes varicus</i>	34	78	87	54	87	679	123	55	23	54	90	12	98	87	56	43	67	67	1794
Mytilidae																			
<i>Mytilis edulis</i>	8	3	5	12	9	8	12	6	12	11	7	12	10	0	14	13	21	24	187
Limacidae																			
<i>Limacus flavus</i>	12	11	0	5	10	12	15	18	19	27	32	11	9	32	12	11	18	17	271
Total number of individuals per square	649	569	351	568	333	129	693	318	323	331	466	513	797	552	369	359	565	695	9744
Total number of species per square	7	7	6	7	6	7	7	7	7	6	7	7	7	6	7	7	7	7	7

Fig. 8. Relative abundance of families

Fig. 9. Rank-abundance diagram of mollusks

The order of abundance of the species inventoried in the Bagoué region is represented by Fig. 9. The analysis of this diagram revealed that there are fewer abundant species and few rare species. A single species (*Achatina fulica*: 52.23%) presents an abundance greater than 5000 individuals. Another species (*Lanistes varicus*: 18.41%) is over 1700 individuals. Two others (*Archachatina ventricosa*: 10.17% and *Limicolaria flammea*: 9.93%) represent 991 and 968 individuals respectively.

Fig. 10. Seasonal variation of the main species of Molluscs in the microhabitats of the semi-open habitat (HSO)

LDS: Long Dry Season LRS: Long Rainy Season
 in the ground: IG; on the floor and/or in the litter: F/L; on the wood and/or trunk: W/T; on leaves and stems: L/S;

Seasonal variation in mollusc abundance in microhabitats

The abundance of molluscs varies from one season to the next. Within the semi-open habitat (Fig. 10), the species *Archachatina ventricosa* (56.12%) and *Limicolaria flammea* (30.09%) are the most abundant in the soil in the dry season. On the ground and litter, it is the Achatinidae family, namely *Archachatina ventricosa* (45.22%) and *Limicolaria flammea* (31.11%) and *Achatina fulica* (31.04%). No taxa are encountered on the wood, trunk, leaves and

stems in the dry season. In rivers and lowlands, the species *Mytilis edulis* (45.17%) was the most important.

As for the rainy season, the species *Archachatina ventricosa* (42.32%) was the most recorded in the soil. On the ground and litter, *Limicolaria flammea* (50.21%) was the most abundant.

Two taxa are found on the wood, the trunk, the leaves and the stems. These are respectively *Archachatina ventricosa* (54.21%) and *Achatina fulica* (51.14%). In rivers and lowlands the species *Mytilis edulis* (54.20%). In the last microhabitat, the species *Archachatina ventricosa* (49.12%) was recorded.

Fig. 11. Seasonal variation of the main mollusc species in open habitat (HO) microhabitats
LDS: Long Dry Season, LRS: Long Rainy Season
in the ground: IG; on the floor and/or in the litter: F/L; on the wood and/or trunk: W/T; on leaves and stems: L/S; rivers and lowlands: R/L; the hollows of rocks, dead wood and termite mounds: HR/DW/TM

In the open habitat (Fig. 11), during the dry season, in the ground, the species *Archachatina ventricosa* (86.27%) is the most inventoried. While on the ground and litter it is *Achatina fulica* (67.41%) which is predominant. Apart from *Achatina fulica* (4.11%), no other species has been recorded on the wood, trunk, leaves and stems. For rivers and lowlands, *Gabbiella africana* (40.39%) is the most abundant. To finish with the hollows of rocks, woods and old termite mounds, the species *Archachatina ventricosa* (67.22%) is the most abundant. However, in the rainy season, species vary from one microhabitat to another. In the soil, the species *Achatina fulica*

(60.14%) is predominant. While on the ground and litter it is *Limicolaria flammea* (50.11%) which is abundant. On wood, tree trunk, leaves and stems, only the Achatinidae were recorded in quantity with respectively *Archachatina ventricosa* (48.21%), *Achatina fulica* (50.18%) and *Limicolaria flammea* (44.31%).

Table 2. Summary of the seasonal abundance of molluscs in the Bagoué region

Molluscs	Seasonal abundance (ind/ha)	
	Great dry season	Great rainy season
<i>Achatina fulica</i>	324 ± 9,13 ^{a e}	4765 ± 38,84 ^f
<i>Laristes varicus</i>	144 ± 1,02 ^b	1650 ± 15,97 ^g
<i>Archachatina ventricosa</i>	40 ± 3,14 ^c	951 ± 20,25 ^h
<i>Limicolaria flammea</i>	9 ± 0,99 ^d	959 ± 19,86 ^h
<i>Gabbiella africana</i>	135 ± 41,12 ^{a e}	309 ± 38,21 ^{a e}
<i>Limacus flavus</i>	17 ± 10,11 ^d	254 ± 23,28 ^{a e}
<i>Mytilis edulis</i>	36 ± 11,20 ^c	151 ± 21,02 ^b
Total	705	9039

Values of columns indexed by the same letter are not significantly different (Mann-Whitney test not significant; $p > 0.05$)

Regarding rivers and lowlands, the most represented species are *Laristes varicus* (40.42%) and *Gabbiella africana* (35.29%). The species *Archachatina ventricosa* (57.22%) is the majority in the hollows of rocks, woods and old termite mounds. The balance of seasonal abundance in the two types of habitats is recorded in Table 2. The species *Achatina fulica*, *Laristes varicus* and *Gabbiella africana* are more abundant in the dry season with respectively 324 ± 9.13; 144 ± 1.02 and 135 ± 41.12 individuals / ha than the other four species. While in the humid period, it is the *Achatina fulica* species which is the most abundant with 4765 ± 38.84 individuals/ha. The *Limicolaria flammea* species is the lowest in the dry season (09 ± 0.99 individuals/ha). However, *Mytilis edulis* is the lowest species in the rainy season (151 ± 5.86 individuals/ha). So, during the dry season, 705 molluscs were recorded. On the other hand, during the wet period, 9039 molluscs were inventoried.

Discussion

The results of our work carried out in the Bagoué region from January 2018 to December 2019, made it

possible to highlight seven species of gastropod molluscs divided into five families: family Achatinidae (*Achatina fulica*, *Archachatina ventricosa*, *Limicolaria flammea*), family Ampullariidae (*Laristes varicus*), family Bithyniidae (*Gabbiella africana*), family Limacidae (*Limacus flavus*) and the Mytilidae family (*Mytilis edulis*). The presence of these species could be explained by the fact that the study environment is favorable to the development of these molluscs. Our results are in agreement with those of Otchoumou (2005) who reports that above 30°C and below 65% relative humidity, the activity of Achatinidae (growth) would be inhibited. Other studies carried out on molluscs in Africa identify four species in Togo (*Archachatina degneri*, *Archachatina marginata*, *Achatina achatina* and *Achatina fulica*), three main species consumed in the Central African Republic: *A. achatina*, *A. fulica* and *A. marginata* (Mbétid - Bessane, 2006) and four species in Côte d'Ivoire: *Archachatina marginata*, *Archachatina ventricosa*, *Achatina fulica* and *Achatina achatina* (Sika, 2015). In addition to favorable climatic conditions, the presence of these molluscs could also depend on their ability to adapt to different environments. *Achatina fulica* is a ubiquitous species that can adapt to diverse soils or climates (Kouassi, 2008). The study of the specific abundance of molluscs revealed that the species *Achatina fulica*, *Laristes varicus*, *Archachatina ventricosa* and *Limicolaria flammea* are very abundant. Indeed, certain reasons could justify this fact. Climatically, these molluscs, due to their geographical distribution, are species that could withstand a wide range of temperature, rainfall and relative humidity. Culinarily, its molluscs are not consumed by the indigenous population; which favors the development of these species.

Also, the study of the monthly abundance of Achatinidae revealed the strong presence of these animals in the environment, from June to August. These months are the wettest of the year. However, this abundance varies according to the seasons. Thus, during the dry period, only the semi-open habitat (I: rock joints, termite mounds) recorded the

Achatinidae. Thus, the adequate temperature in termite mounds and in the cavities of weathering rocks (joints) could offer an ideal refuge for aestivating Achatinidae, which could be explained by the fact that this stratum offered these molluscs a microclimate favorable to their aestivation. Our results are in agreement with those of Sawadogo *et al.* (2012). These authors report that during the day, the average temperatures were around 33.3 ± 1.5 °C in the ambient environment and 29.4 ± 0.5 °C in the termite mound. During the night, they were 27.7 ± 0.5 °C in the termite mound and 26.2 ± 0.7 °C in the ambient environment. However, in humid periods, Achatinidae were found in all study areas. The open habitat with its three subgroups (IIa: grassy savannah, regrowth of shrubs, IIb: proximity to a river, IIc: fruit tree) recorded the maximum number of Achatinidae. This abundance would be due to rainfall favorable to the rise in relative humidity of the air and to the general regrowth of the plant cover and the abundance of mangoes and the fruits of shea and néré. According to Memel (2009), the species *Achatina fulica* and *Archachatina ventricosa* adapt easily to low humidity and high humidity. But in general, molluscs are attracted to moist habitats. They like humid environments with high rainfall. Rain increases the relative humidity of the environment.

These factors are favorable to the activities of these animals (Codjia and Noumonvi, 2002).

This could justify the high collection of snails in the rainy season (June, July, August) compared to the dry season (February, March, April, May). Climate data seems to support this fact.

In the Bagoué region, two types of habitats have been described. These are semi-open habitat and open habitat. Within these two types of habitats, microhabitats have been defined. Thus, on the ground and/or in the litter (G/L), in the soil (S) and the specific richness was maximum for both types of habitats and whatever the season. The Achatinidae family, unevenly distributed, is the most represented. This presence could be explained by the fact that

these molluscs find their food in the litter and the ground. Our results are consistent with those of Amani (2018) and Jess (1989). These authors maintain that molluscs obtain 40% of their nutrients from the soil. Also, the uneven distribution of species is mentioned by Patil *et al.* (2012) and Kayeye *et al.* (2014) in India and Congo respectively.

Also, depending on the microhabitats, the Shannon diversity index is maximum for the soil and/or litter regardless of the type of habitat exploited. Which means that this microhabitat is more colonized by molluscs. The presence of litter would constitute a feeding niche for these molluscs. It would also be an ideal shelter during times of drought and shelter from certain predators. Our results are in agreement with those of Tattersfield (1996), Darmedji (2009), Oke and Chokor (2009), Memel (2009) and Amani (2018). These authors reported that most of the terrestrial malacofauna lived in this microhabitat. Also, Meyer *et al.* (2013) reported that litter is essential for the survival of many terrestrial molluscs. Furthermore, the molluscs are the only ones recorded in all microhabitats. They are constantly in contact with the soil, certainly in search of minerals (iron, calcium, magnesium, etc.) resulting from the decomposition of the leaves. Our results are in agreement with those of N'dri (2015) in the forest of Nangui Abrogoua University and N'dri (2021) at the national floristic center at the University of Cocody Abidjan.

Taxonomic richness, with respect to seasons, was more abundant in the rainy season than in the dry season. Also, microhabitats such as in the ground (G), on the ground and/or litter (G/L), on leaves and stems (L/S), the Achatinidae family was the most abundant. This abundance is significant in the rainy season. However, no species was recorded on wood and trunk (W/T) and on leaves and stems (L/S) in the dry season regardless of the habitat type (semi-open or open). This could be explained by the fact that these molluscs prefer humid environments. Our results corroborate those of Amani (2018). In addition, humidity constitutes an important factor for

their biological activities (nutrition and reproduction) (Takeda and Ozaki, 1986; Otchoumou, 1997).

Conclusion

At the end of our study, it appears that in the natural environment, the abundance of the 7 species of molluscs collected (*Achatina fulica*, *Archachatina ventricosa*, *Limicolaria flammea*, *Laristes varicus*, *Gabbiella africana*, *Limacus flavus* and *Mytilis edulis*) varies according to the seasons; so in the dry season, these molluscs are almost impossible to find. We observed them in semi-open habitats during aestivation. However, in the rainy season, they colonize both open and semi-open habitats. It emerges from our study that the populations of Bagoué, through their activities (bush fires, deforestation, slash-and-burn cultivation), contribute enormously to the disruption of the environment, which could represent a danger for the survival of the molluscs in this region.

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